

Ensemble model aggregation using a computationally lightweight machine-learning model to forecast ocean waves

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Abstract

This study investigated an approach to improve the accuracy of computationally lightweight surrogate models by updating forecasts based on historical accuracy relative to sparse observation data. Using a lightweight, ocean-wave forecasting model, we created a large number of model ensembles, with perturbed inputs, for a two-year study period. Forecasts were aggregated using a machine-learning algorithm that combined forecasts from multiple, independent models into a single “best-estimate” prediction of the true state. The framework was applied to a case-study site in Monterey Bay, California. A learning-aggregation technique used historical observations and model forecasts to calculate a weight for each ensemble member. Weighted ensemble predictions were compared to measured wave conditions to evaluate performance against present state-of-the-art. Finally, we discussed how this framework, which integrates ensemble aggregations and surrogate mod-

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els, can be used to improve forecasting systems and further enable scientific process studies.

1 **1. Introduction**

2 In recent decades, science has made significant advances in enabling ma-
3 chines to understand language and process images for applications such as fa-
4 cial recognition, image classification, text translation, and autonomous driv-
5 ing. More generally, machine learning applied to other scientific domains,
6 particularly the geosciences, are in a nascent stage. Some examples include
7 applying artificial neural networks to simulate earthquake-cycle activity [1],
8 accelerating Eulerian fluid simulations using convolutional neural networks
9 [2], up-scaling air pollution forecasting using deep learning [3], and research
10 to combine physics-based rules to guide machine-learning models of temper-
11 ature profiles in a lake [4].

12 A computationally lightweight emulator (a surrogate for more complex
13 systems) has a number of advantages, such as near real-time simulations over
14 long time scales (e. g., multi-year studies of ocean conditions); the computa-
15 tional expedience of surrogate models is also important for systems affected
16 by uncertainties in initial and boundary conditions such as risk-assessment
17 studies that require iterative scenario modelling [5, 6, 7]. A wide range of
18 analyses across different disciplines can benefit from such reduced computa-
19 tional complexity [8]. Examples where uncertainty is a major factor include
20 Bayesian model calibration [9, 10], global sensitivity analyses [11, 12, 7], and
21 Monte Carlo-based uncertainty or reliability analyses [13, 14, 15].

22 There is a growing trend in the geosciences to combine deterministic and

23 probabilistic tools to provide stakeholders with most likely forecasts together
24 with confidence bounds on alternative outcomes [16]. This is particularly
25 true in oceanography where large uncertainties exist related to fundamental
26 aspects such as the physics of wind input, dissipation, and nonlinear inter-
27 actions [17]. Here, we combine ensemble-forecasting and machine-learning
28 techniques to: (1) investigate uncertainty from an ensemble modelling sys-
29 tem with perturbed inputs, (2) leverage the advantages of computationally
30 lightweight surrogate models, and (3) generate a forecast that is better than
31 the best individual model prediction.

32 The authors recently developed and demonstrated a machine-learning
33 surrogate model for a physics-based ocean-wave model [18]. The model gen-
34 erated a nonlinear mapping of inputs (i. e. wave height, period, and direction
35 boundary conditions, spatially variable ocean currents, and wind speeds)
36 to computed outputs (spatially variable significant wave height, H_s , and
37 characteristic wave period, T). The machine-learning model yielded enor-
38 mous speedup (>five-thousand-fold) in computational time while maintain-
39 ing accuracy that was well within the confidence bounds of the physics-based
40 model.

41 Ensemble forecasts of wave conditions are typically generated from statis-
42 tical perturbations of wave-height boundary data, ocean-current input data,
43 wind forcing (particularly for global models), model physics, discretisation,
44 and parameterisation schemes [19]. The fundamental objective of ensemble
45 forecasting is to investigate inherent uncertainty to provide more accurate
46 information about future states. This process facilitates transition from sin-
47 gle, deterministic forecasting with optimistic assumptions on the fidelity of

48 model inputs, to a multiple, probabilistic forecasting approach that realisti-
49 cally considers errors and uncertainties in the model forcing data and fun-
50 damental governing equations. Ensemble aggregation techniques can extend
51 from simple arithmetic averages of all models to machine-learning approaches
52 that admit aggregate ensemble predictions based on weighted summation
53 [20]. The learning-aggregation technique makes use of historical observa-
54 tions and model forecasts to produce a weight for each model. A linear,
55 convex (i. e., where weights are constrained so they sum to unity) combina-
56 tion of model forecasts is performed with these weights to generate the best
57 model forecast.

58 This study focused on an ensemble forecasting approach applied at a
59 case-study site in Monterey Bay, California. Ensembles were created based
60 on a careful analysis of model sensitivity to input data at three buoy lo-
61 cations. Model aggregation considered three approaches: (1) naïve model
62 aggregation, (2) ridge-regression forecasting, and (3) forecasting using the
63 exponentiated-gradient method. The paper presents a comprehensive frame-
64 work to develop and aggregate ensemble model elements cognisant of the
65 inherent uncertainties of inputs.

66 Our objective is to leverage the advantages of computationally lightweight
67 surrogate models and non-invasive, ensemble aggregation techniques to pro-
68 vide the best-estimate of the system state. The contributions of the paper
69 are as follows:

- 70 • Framework that combines computationally lightweight surrogates and
71 ensemble modelling to improve predictive skill.
- 72 • Ensemble generation implementation to fully explore the solution space

73 based on case-study conditions and sensitivity to model boundary con-
74 ditions.

- 75 • Analysis of data-driven ensemble aggregation techniques and the im-
76 provement in predictive skill compared to deterministic approaches.

77 **2. Methodology**

78 In this section, we briefly describe the study site; development of the
79 surrogate ocean wave model is described in detail elsewhere [18]. Section
80 2.3.1 describes the creation of the model ensemble elements whereby the
81 surrogate model is run multiple times with perturbed inputs based on an
82 analysis of system dynamics. Finally, we describe the aggregation techniques
83 adopted that considered two different methods to compute weights for each
84 ensemble model element based on historical agreement with observations.

85 *2.1. Study site*

86 Monterey Bay is a wide and partly deep (>1000 m) embayment in cen-
87 tral California, broadly open to the ocean. It is an important economic and
88 ecological location home to a federally protected national marine sanctuary
89 (montereybay.noaa.gov) and a number of state marine sanctuaries [21]. It
90 is a well-studied site with several National Oceanic and Atmospheric Ad-
91 ministration National Data Buoy Center (NOAA NDBC) buoys providing
92 measurements of wave and wind characteristics dating as far back as 1987.
93 The relative richness of observational data and well-studied dynamics makes
94 Monterey Bay an ideal location to explore data-driven approaches.

Figure 1: Mean wave period (blue curves) and direction (red curves) at the outermost buoy (Buoy 46042 in Figure 2). The y axis on the left-hand side represents direction while the right quantifies wave period. To better visualise primary trends, low-pass-filtered values are also shown (heavy curves)

95 The oceanography of Monterey Bay is closely tied to processes of the Cal-
 96 ifornia Current, a 1,200 km broad and 300 m deep surface current that trans-
 97 ports water of subarctic origin southward along the North American coast
 98 at 15 to 30 cm/s [22]. Within the coastal regime, sea surface flow undergoes
 99 a seasonal reversal. During the late autumn and winter the direction is pri-
 100 marily to the north, while flow to the south dominates during the spring and
 101 summer driven by the intensification of northwesterly winds. These ocean-
 102 graphic trends influence wave conditions, with greater wave-heights during

103 winter, and higher numbers of short-period locally generated waves during
104 winter than during summer [23]. Figure 1 plots measurements of dominant
105 wave period and direction from a site in the outer bay (Buoy 46042 q.v.
106 Figure 2) over a five-year interval. Observed waves were a combination of
107 long-period (10–20 s) swells and short-period (8–10 s) locally generated wind
108 waves with period varying between eight and 20 seconds. The low-pass fil-
109 tered values demonstrated these seasonal trends with the raw data exhibiting
110 the fluctuating characteristics of oceanic waves. A prediction framework for
111 ocean waves aims to capture both longer-term seasonal trends and small-scale
112 fluctuations of these processes.

113 *2.2. Machine-learning Surrogate Model*

114 One of the challenges of applying machine learning to the geosciences is
115 the enormous volumes of data required to train the model notwithstanding
116 the amount of sensor data that can be available, which are often spatially
117 sparse and intermittent. However, when developing a machine-learning sur-
118 rogate for a physics-based model, there is the luxury of being able to run the
119 model as many times as necessary to develop a sufficient data set for training.
120 The Simulating WAVes Nearshore (SWAN) model is the industry-standard
121 wave-modelling tool developed at the Delft University of Technology that
122 computes wave fields in coastal waters forced by wave conditions on the do-
123 main boundaries, ocean currents, and winds [24].

124 To learn features of wave conditions, a supervised machine-learning model
125 based on a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) network was used to compute sig-
126 nificant wave heights, H_s . During training, where the network was presented
127 with examples of the computation it was learning (i. e., SWAN model runs),

128 an optimisation problem was solved until the output of the network’s last
 129 layer consistently approximated the training data set (in this case, the H_s
 130 field). Within a supervised-learning framework, inputs and outputs of the
 131 model were provided and the model learned optimised weights and biases
 132 that replicate the nonlinear relationship between inputs and outputs.

133 The MLP [25] model was trained at the Monterey Bay study site. Fig-
 134 ure 2 illustrates the modelling domain (64×54 -km² discretised across 71×48
 135 computational elements providing a horizontal resolution of 0.01° each ap-
 136 proximately equal to $900 \times 1,000$ m²) for the SWAN model originally de-
 137 veloped and validated by Chang et al. [26]. NOAA NDBC Buoys 46042
 138 (white), 46114 (red), and 46240 (green) provided measurements of wave con-
 139 ditions together with other ocean and meteorological data reported every 30
 140 to 60 minutes. Inputs to the SWAN model comprised boundary-condition
 141 wave data extracted from Buoy 46042 (Figure 2), ocean-current data from
 142 a Regional Ocean modelling System (ROMS) hydrodynamic model of Mon-
 143 terey Bay [27], and historical wind data from The Weather Company (TWC).
 144 These were assembled into machine-learning input vectors, \mathbf{x} , with outputs
 145 corresponding to the SWAN-simulated H_s field, \mathbf{y} . Design matrices were de-
 146 veloped by completing 11,078 SWAN model runs dating back to the archived
 147 extent of ROMS currents nowcasts (from April 1st, 2013 to June 30th, 2017)
 148 and stacking \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} into design matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} , respectively.

Because the goal of this effort was to develop a machine-learning frame-
 work to act as a surrogate for the SWAN model, the nonlinear function
 mapping inputs to the best representation of outputs, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, was sought:

$$g(\mathbf{x}; \Theta) = \hat{\mathbf{y}}. \tag{1}$$

149 A sufficiently trained machine-learning model yields a mapping matrix,
 150 Θ , that acts as a surrogate for the SWAN model. This facilitated sidestep-
 151 ping of the SWAN model by replacing the solution to its partial differential
 152 equation of wave energy density with the data-driven machine-learning model
 153 composed of the vector-matrix operations encapsulated in (1).

Figure 2: SWAN model domain with color indicating bathymetric depth. The three buoys used to verify the model are indicated with the symbols where the white diamond is Buoy 46042, the red diamond is Buoy 46114, and the green diamond is Buoy 46240. Wave characteristics, H_s , T , and direction, from nearby Buoy 46042 were specified along ocean boundaries indicated in red, TWC winds were specified at the 12 turquoise circles, and currents were specified at the 357 nodes of the ROMS model indicated with black dots.

154 MLP regression was used to reproduce the SWAN-generated H_s field, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$.
155 Fundamental performance was assessed by comparing against the spatially
156 variable SWAN H_s predictions, \mathbf{y} . The \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} data were randomly shuf-
157 fled into two groups to form the training dataset composed of 90% of the
158 11,078 rows of data with the testing dataset the remaining 10%. Mapping
159 matrix Θ was calculated using the training dataset and then applied to the
160 testing dataset and the RMSE between test data, \mathbf{y} , and its machine-learning
161 estimate, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, was calculated.

162 The machine-learning model demonstrated excellent performance against
163 the SWAN model with RMSE ≈ 9 cm, notably less than the confidence
164 bounds of the model (about 40 to 50 cm [28]). Further, the computational
165 time to make forecasts was reduced by a factor of 1/5,000th. Comparison
166 against measured buoy data revealed the main limitation of surrogate mod-
167 elling – a surrogate model will never outperform the model it emulates and
168 the most well-designed surrogate can only aspire to match the accuracy of
169 the more expensive model.

170 *2.3. Integrating Forecasts with Machine-learning Aggregation*

171 *2.3.1. Creation of Model Ensembles*

172 As discussed previously, ensemble forecasting typically focuses on mul-
173 tiple simulations where anything from physical parametrisations, numerical
174 discretisation, or input data are perturbed. Machine learning models do not
175 readily admit adjustments to model parameters (indeed, that contravenes
176 the data-driven philosophy of the approach); instead, ensemble construction
177 focused on perturbation of model inputs. Inputs to the ML surrogate model
178 consisted of lateral boundary information on wave height, period and di-

179 rection, and spatially variable ocean currents and wind speeds, which were
180 prescribed at hourly intervals over the simulation period. Previous stud-
181 ies investigating the sensitivity of the Monterey Bay SWAN model to per-
182 turbed inputs of wind forcing (extracted from the NOAA Global Ensemble
183 Forecast System or GEFS) demonstrated low sensitivity to perturbation of
184 wind and ocean current inputs [29]. As a result of the limited spatial scale
185 of the Monterey Bay model domain ($\approx 3,500 \text{ km}^2$), perturbing wind input
186 data based on outputs from NOAA GEFS forecasts yielded changes in wave
187 height of less than 0.5 cm. Considering this lack of sensitivity, and to sim-
188 plify the ensemble-generation process, only lateral-boundary wave data were
189 perturbed.

190 As described in Section 2.2, lateral boundary data to the model were
191 prescribed based on wave measurements extracted from Buoy 46042 (Figure
192 2). This served as the deterministic, or benchmark, model for the study
193 (best individual model). Creation of perturbed wave boundary conditions
194 emanated from these data by: (1) defining the upper and lower thresholds
195 and (2) quantifying system dynamics based on the spread around the wave
196 time-series data, which were superimposed on the above thresholds. Upper
197 and lower thresholds for H_s were defined as the maximum and minimum
198 daily values (red curves in Figure 3). To this, a random perturbation was
199 added to represent the statistical dynamics of the system. The perturbation
200 was estimated from a random Gaussian process model [30] with distribution
201 of mean zero and spread computed from the 48-hour rolling window standard
202 deviation of the observations.

203 Final upper and lower thresholds (green curve in Figure 3), were gen-

Figure 3: Time series of H_s from which perturbed values were selected for boundary-data specification. The blue points are measured data, the red curves span the daily maximum/minimum, and the green curves include Gaussian perturbations to incorporate variable system dynamics.

204 erated from combination of these perturbations and boundary wave height
 205 data for model ensembles were sampled from within these limits. Sixteen
 206 model ensembles were created by sampling boundary wave height data using
 207 a standard Latin hypercube sampling (LHS) technique; a statistical method
 208 for generating a near-random sample of parameter values from a distribution
 209 [31]. LHS proceeds by dividing a distribution or range into N (in this case
 210 16), equally probable intervals (in this case, the range at each point in time is
 211 bounded by the green curves in Figure 3) and a random sample was selected

212 from within each interval. This ensured adequate coverage of a distribution
 213 where the tails are important – a pertinent consideration for wave forecasting
 214 where accurately predicting maximum wave heights may be more important
 215 than capturing ambient conditions.

Figure 4: (a) Northwest-prevailing wave directions during the study period. (b) Boundary-condition wave direction perturbations were randomly selected from the four bins. Directions are presented in the meteorological convention.

216 Further analysis of model forecasts indicated that the ensembles with
 217 perturbed wave-height forcing did not fully capture dynamics at the near-
 218 shore Buoy 46240 (analysed in more detail by O’Donncha et al. [29]). In
 219 particular, the model failed to capture wave conditions developed when swells
 220 were from the southeast. To ensure the ensemble spread fully captured the
 221 dynamical space, wave directions were perturbed in a similar manner to wave
 222 heights, namely:

- 223 • Upper and lower thresholds were created from the daily maximum and

224 minimum of measured wave directions.

- 225 • A random component was added to represent sensor uncertainty and
226 system dynamics. As for wave height, the random component was
227 sampled from a normal distribution of mean zero and spread computed
228 from the standard deviation of the measured wave direction.

229 These produced upper and lower limits on wave directions at each point in
230 time from which wave directions were sampled using the LHS technique. Six
231 ensemble elements with perturbed directional inputs were created. A total
232 of 119 ensemble elements were generated – 16 with perturbed wave heights,
233 six with perturbed directions, and one each with unperturbed height and
234 direction.

235 Classical works on ensemble forecasting demonstrated that the ensemble
236 mean should give a better forecast than a single deterministic forecast as long
237 as the ensemble represents the uncertainty present in the forecast [32, 33].
238 It is therefore critical that the ensemble spread encapsulate observed dy-
239 namics. Ensemble generation methods generally focus on uncertainties in:
240 (1) initial conditions and (2) forcing data (uncertainty of model equations
241 and parametrisation are also often considered). Ensemble methods with per-
242 turbed initial conditions are ubiquitous in meteorology and these focus on
243 quantifying the fastest growing errors with techniques such as the breeder
244 method and optimal perturbation analysis, common in data-assimilation im-
245 plementations [34]. Specification of lateral boundary conditions for ensemble
246 models is usually either from ensemble predictions on larger domains (such
247 as the NOAA GFS) or from perturbation around a deterministic estimate
248 or observation [35]. Evensen [36] described the required characteristics of an

Figure 5: Time-series representation of generated ensembles (116 individual elements) upon perturbing H_s and D . Curves represent individual forecasts for each ensemble member and the black circles denote observations from Buoy (a) 46114 and (b) 46240.

249 ensemble set of models as: including sufficient spread to capture pertinent
 250 dynamics, and that each model or ensemble element be linearly independent.

251 For an ensemble aggregation study, the ensemble spread and relationship
 252 between individual model elements is a key consideration. Figure 5 presents
 253 the generated ensemble predictions against measured data for a representa-
 254 tive six-month period at the outer-bay and near-shore buoy locations. The
 255 ensemble spread captured by the models was clearly sufficient to encapsulate
 256 observed dynamics, particularly at the near-shore buoy that proved more

257 sensitive to perturbed forcing. It is worth noting that one of the primary
258 focus of the ensemble generation was ensuring that system dynamics were
259 fully encapsulated by the ensemble spread – this allowed a pragmatic ap-
260 proach whereby the ensemble generation was “hand crafted” to some degree
261 to analyse and understand the different combinations of wave height and
262 directions that best captured observed spread at each buoy. This approach
263 was assisted by the low computational cost of the surrogate model (com-
264 pared to the full SWAN model) where different ensemble predictions could
265 be readily computed and analysed – making a two year prediction with all of
266 the 119 ensemble elements took less than 18 minutes compared to 290 days
267 that would be required to run the full SWAN model (on equivalent compute
268 resources). Characteristics of individual ensemble elements were observed
269 to be a complex interplay of prescribed wave height and direction together
270 with the nonlinear dynamics of the MLP model (recall that other forcing
271 such as winds and ocean currents were kept constant across different ensem-
272 ble elements). The objective of the ensemble aggregation can be considered
273 as computing a set of weights to reduce the ensemble set to a unique fore-
274 cast that minimises differences between forecasts and (highly dynamic and
275 variable) observations at multiple buoy locations.

276 *2.3.2. Model aggregation*

277 The underlying assumption of ensemble modelling is that each member
278 contains some information pertinent to the true state of the system. The in-
279 terplay between models is expected to vary in both space and time; i. e., mem-
280 ber models performed better at different points in space and time depending
281 upon ambient conditions, individual model forcing, and other physical in-

282 teractions. Ordinary least squares (OLS) is a widely used approach that
 283 estimates model predictions that minimise the sum of squares of residuals
 284 (against observations). The variance of OLS estimates is high as it pref-
 285 erentially weights the models that yield the best predictive skill at each
 286 point in time (conceptually overfitting to the data). The focus in this study
 287 was to develop an aggregation framework that incorporated historic model
 288 performance while also accounting for seasonal or shorter-term wave con-
 289 dition dynamics. In effect, the aggregation balances historic performance
 290 and short-scale dynamics to aggregate the ensemble predictions into a single
 291 “best-estimate” forecast.

The first technique investigated was a ridge-regression (RR) prediction
 algorithm. In this approach, a weight vector was computed for each time
 update that minimised the difference between past predictions and observa-
 tions. The weight vector for each time was [20]:

$$\mathbf{u}_t = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n} \left[\lambda \|\mathbf{u}\|_2^2 + \sum_{t'=1}^{t-1} \sum_{s \in S_{t'}} (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{t'}^s - y_{t'}^s)^2 \right], \quad (2)$$

292 where $\mathbf{x}_{t'}^s$ is a vector of dimension \mathcal{N} (number of ensembles equal to 116)
 293 containing the prediction from each ensemble member at time t' (for each
 294 station s), $y_{t'}^s$ represents observations at time t' and station s , \mathbf{u}_t is vector
 295 of weights computed for each ensemble member at time t , $S_{t'}$ represents the
 296 number of observation stations for which data are available at each time, and
 297 λ serves as a regularisation constant used to keep the magnitude of \mathbf{u}_t small
 298 and to reduce variation between consecutive vectors. Mallet et al. [20] de-
 299 scribed this regularisation (penalty) function, which is typically selected in a
 300 bespoke manner for each study to balance contributions from the most recent

301 model-observation datasets and historical data. As λ tends toward zero, the
 302 regression tends toward an OLS solution. Conceptually, the objective was
 303 to assign weights to each ensemble member that minimised the MSE across
 304 observation stations (Buoys 46114 and 46240). Training the weights vector
 305 progressed on all data to $t - 1$ whereupon predictions were made for the next
 306 time step, t , based on the most recent ensemble predictions.

The computed weights were then used to make a forecast, \hat{x}_t^s , for each station, s , at time t as:

$$\hat{x}_t^s = \mathbf{u}_t \cdot \mathbf{x}_t^s = \sum_{m=1}^{\mathcal{N}} u_{m,t} x_{m,t}^s, \quad (3)$$

307 where \mathbf{x}_t^s is each member of the ensemble prediction at station s , and \mathbf{u}_t is
 308 the weight vector applied to each prediction.

The second technique explored here was an exponentiated-gradient (EG) algorithm for linear predictors [37]. The EG algorithm also has a weight vector, \mathbf{u}_t , used to predict $\hat{x}_t^s = \mathbf{u}_t \cdot \mathbf{x}_t^s$. The updated weight for each ensemble member $x_{m,t'}$ was [37]:

$$u_{m,t} = \frac{\sum_{t'=1}^{t-1} r_{m,t'} u_{m,t'}}{\sum_{j=1}^{\mathcal{N}} \sum_{t'=1}^{t-1} r_{j,t'} u_{j,t'}}, \quad (4)$$

for all $m = 1, \dots, \mathcal{N}$, and:

$$r_{m,t'} = \exp \left[\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_{t'}} -2\mu(\mathbf{u}_{t'} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{t'}^s - y_{t'}^s) x_{m,t'}^s \right],$$

309 where μ is the learning rate.

310 Weights computed with the EG approach were normalised by the sum
 311 of all weights as expressed by (4). This constrains the weights to a con-
 312 vex combination as opposed to the unconstrained weights admitted by RR
 313 (i. e., where weights could take any values that minimised the loss function).
 314 A potential advantage of EG-type approaches over RR is this constraint
 315 on weights, which limits rapid fluctuations. As opposed to unconstrained
 316 weights, convex-combination weight vectors may better extend to other re-
 317 gions of the model domain away from where observations are available [20].
 318 EG predictions will always fall within the envelope of the ensemble predic-
 319 tions, which avoids unrealistic model forecasting.

A further aspect of the weight computation was selection of the historical window length. A naïve approach uses all available historical data while more sophisticated implementations acknowledge that performance in the recent past can be more indicative of predictive skill. Amending (2) for RR aggregation to incorporate user-specified window lengths, t_w , yielded:

$$\mathbf{u}_t = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u} \in R^n} \left[\lambda \|\mathbf{u}\|_2^2 + \sum_{t'=t-t_w}^{t-1} \sum_{s \in S_{t'}} (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{t'}^s - y_{t'}^s)^2 \right], \quad (5)$$

320 which differs from (2) only in the starting index, $t - t_w$. Similar to selection
 321 of the learning rate, μ , and the regularisation constant, λ , a cross-validation
 322 approach was adopted to identify the optimum t_w . We expand on the im-
 323 portance of judicious selection of these parameters and the challenges of
 324 providing general recommendations on appropriate choices in Section 3.

325 **3. Results and Discussion**

326 Analysis of the results and performance of the aggregation technique fo-
327 cused on the two-year period, 2012–2014. Model aggregation consisted of
328 an on-line forecasting tool using past data to update weights. Weights were
329 initialised as zero vector or with value $1/\mathcal{N}$ (i. e., assigning equal weight to
330 each prediction) for the RR and EG forecasters, respectively, and their values
331 updated at each model forecast time based on a minimisation of the differ-
332 ence between forecast and observation. A number of prediction periods were
333 considered to evaluate the performance of the approach in improving one-,
334 two- and three-day dynamic forecasts.

335 Figure 6 presents a selection of model weights computed with the RR and
336 EG aggregation methods for a representative one-month period. Most mod-
337 els contributed to the aggregated forecast with the majority of weights having
338 strongly non-zero values. Further, the dynamics and variations of the weight-
339 ing aggregation over time are apparent with larger-magnitude weights corre-
340 sponding to periods with larger spreads in model forecasts (and consequently
341 higher uncertainties from the ensemble-prediction perspective). During pe-
342 riods of large model spread, minimisation of model-observation differences
343 was facilitated by applying large weights to models that performed well and
344 low weights to models that performed poorly. The time evolution and vari-
345 ations of weights were sensitive to a number of factors, namely, observation
346 variance, regularisation coefficients, window length, and model prediction
347 accuracy. Figure 6 demonstrates that EG weights tended to reduce in mag-
348 nitude over the period presented (note that EG weights are constrained to
349 sum to one). This is largely due to a combination of observation variance

Figure 6: Weights computed for a representative subset (25) of the 116-member model ensemble over a one-month period. LHS represents RR weights while RHS represents those from EG. Each curve represents the weight, $u_{m,t}$, attached to an individual model and shows its evolution over time.

350 and the constrained nature of the weights for EG.

351 A key consideration in wave forecasting is the temporal dynamics of
 352 the system. The fundamental basis of weighted model aggregation is that
 353 there is a certain relationship between successive forecasts and observations;
 354 i. e., there is a likelihood that the ensemble element that performed best at
 355 time t will be the model that performs best at time $t + 1$. By updating
 356 weights based on the difference between the latest observations and forecast,
 357 it ensured that the best-performing model was assigned the highest weight.

358 This “follow-the-leader” type forecasting system works best if the quan-
 359 tity being modeled is relatively stationary with pronounced historic influence
 360 – ocean waves are highly dynamic with significant temporal variation. Hence,
 361 a key requirement of the approach was to select the parameterisation that
 362 best exploited historical performance while maintaining the ability to adjust
 363 to rapidly changing wave measurements. A series of cross-validation experi-

Figure 7: Contour plot of MAPE computed from a 24-hour RR aggregation forecast as a function of window size, t_w , and regularisation constant λ for the two-year study period.

364 ments were used to select the most appropriate value for the regularisation
 365 constant or learning rate for RR and EG, respectively, and also to select the
 366 optimal t_w . Namely, for both RR and EG, 500 experiments were conducted
 367 that varied λ , μ , and t_w . To guide the selection process, minimum values
 368 were specified to avoid overfitting. For both λ and μ , a minimum value of
 369 1.5×10^{-10} was specified, while a minimum value of 24 hours was specified
 370 for t_w .

371 For each cross-validation experiment, a 24-hour forecast was produced
 372 (creating a total of 730 forecasts for the two-year period), and the MAPE

373 was computed against observations. Figure 7 presents MAPE for RR as a
374 function of λ , and t_w . Results demonstrated the need to balance short-term
375 dynamics and model skill. As λ and t_w tended toward zero, the aggrega-
376 tion reduces to a weight generation that minimised residuals between the
377 model and observations (in effect, fitting the prediction to the data). This
378 does not provide appreciable predictive skill as noise in the system can dom-
379 inate (i. e., a model that happened to perform well at a given point in time
380 tended to be weighted heavily and a model that had good long-term predic-
381 tive skill could be excessively punished for short-timescale deviations) and
382 dynamic forecasting skill is sacrificed. For short t_w (< 48 hours), results
383 demonstrated high MAPE as the computed weights were not representative
384 of system dynamics. Predictive skill was not as sensitive to the specifica-
385 tion of regularisation constant with a general trend of increased MAPE for
386 $\lambda > 0.6$. Results demonstrated that $t_w = 524$ hours and $\lambda = 0.18$ yielded the
387 lowest MAPE.

388 More generally, appropriate specification of λ and t_w was required to
389 balance the importance of historical performance and short-scale dynamics.
390 In cases with limited sensor data (learning conditions across the bay from
391 two data points), it is important to avoid overfitting. This is particularly
392 relevant in this study where both buoy locations have distinct characteristics
393 (outer-bay and near-shore dynamics). Hence, the cross-validation approach
394 was combined with a judicious selection of parameters that leaned more
395 heavily toward increased dependence on historic effects. Namely, the largest
396 λ and t_w values that produced low MAPEs and that preceded a noticeable
397 increase in MAPE were selected. For this case, $t_w = 928$ hours and $\lambda =$

398 0.34. This can be interpreted as an implementation of the “elbow method”
399 commonly used in clustering approaches that aims to optimally balances
400 error and computational complexity (of increased data size) [38].

401 From these cross-validation studies, hyperparameters t_w , λ , and μ that
402 minimised MAPE were specified and forecasts were created from the ag-
403 gregated model predictions. Results were compared against two benchmark
404 forecasts:

- 405 • Best individual forecast defined as the model with unperturbed inputs.
- 406 • Ensemble average consisting of the average of all ensemble forecasts
407 (equivalent to applying a weight of $1/\mathcal{N}$ to each element).

408 Figure 8 compares 24 hour forecasts at both sensor locations (Buoy 46240
409 and 46114 in Figure 2) to observations. Results demonstrated that an aggre-
410 gation that took into account historical model performance through weighted
411 averaging outperformed more naïve approaches. MAPE was reduced from
412 22.2% for a deterministic model with unperturbed inputs (green curve) to
413 11.7% for the RR aggregation (black curve) and 12.1% for the EG method
414 (blue curve). RR outperformed EG largely due to the unconstrained weights,
415 which can more quickly react to rapid changes in a volatile system. This re-
416 duced errors, but may yield overfitting; the constrained nature of the EG
417 weights may be more robust and applied farther from observation stations
418 with more confidence than the unconstrained RR [20].

419 Table 1 lists the MAPE for each model implementation for different fore-
420 casting windows. It is worth noting that the weight computation selected
421 those that provided best agreement averaged across buoys data rather than

Figure 8: 24-hour predictions of H_s (curves) plotted against observations (orange dots) at Buoy (a) 46114 and (b) 46240. The black curve denotes forecasts aggregated by RR. The dashed blue curve represents EG aggregation. The dashed green curve represents the best element from the 119-member ensemble, while the purple curve is the arithmetic average across all model forecasts. The top figure presents predictions plotted against observations, while the bottom figure presents MAPE for each prediction.

Table 1: MAPE (%) for each model scenario at each buoy, and averaged across both buoys. MAPEs are presented for three prediction windows, a 24-, 48-, and 72-hour predictions, respectively (second row). The model scenarios presented are best individual ensemble model element (BI), arithmetic average of all ensemble elements (AA), and ridge regression (RR) and exponentiated gradient (EG) aggregation.

Buoy	BI			AA			RR			EG		
	24	48	72	24	48	72	24	48	72	24	48	72
46114	7.1	7.1	7.1	7.6	7.6	7.6	6.7	6.9	7.2	7.1	7.3	8.0
46240	37.3	37.3	37.3	23.7	23.7	23.7	16.8	17.2	16.7	17.2	17.5	18.1
Average	22.2	22.2	22.2	15.6	15.6	15.6	11.7	12.1	12.0	12.1	12.4	13.0

422 either in isolation. Further, each buoy have distinct environmental condi-
 423 tion, namely, open-ocean conditions (Buoy 46114) and sheltered, near-land
 424 conditions (Buoy 46240), as evident in Figure 8. The resultant aggregation
 425 generated a best-estimate forecast of ocean conditions across the available
 426 buoy locations and hence may be more applicable far from the buoy loca-
 427 tions (i. e., at arbitrary locations within the bay). For all forecasting win-
 428 dows, ensemble aggregation significantly outperformed a single forecast with
 429 unperturbed inputs. A naïve aggregation based on a simple ensemble aver-
 430 age reduced MAPE by 30%, while RR and EG aggregation provided a 47%
 431 and 45% reduction, respectively (for a 24 hour forecasting window). Predic-
 432 tive skill was comparable across different forecasting windows (24, 48, and
 433 72 hours) indicating the robustness of the computed weights and the ability
 434 to produce dynamic forecasts.

435 Two important assumptions were made in this study:

- 436 • The observations are accurate and do not contain any sensor uncer-
 437 tainty or error and
- 438 • The accuracy of the model is similar throughout the spatial domain .

439 These assumptions meant that the aggregation provided equal importance
440 to each observation point. Practical implementations may incorporate fur-
441 ther considerations such as the evolution of uncertainty in observations over
442 time and geographical regions of greater importance for forecasting (e. g., one
443 may prefer a forecasting system that is most accurate near-shore). There is
444 a large body of research on quantifying observation uncertainty, particularly
445 in the data-assimilation literature [39]. Maintaining the common assump-
446 tion that sensor errors are uncorrelated in time, appropriate specification of
447 regularisation and window length (λ , μ , and t_w) parameters tends to exclude
448 high-frequency errors by weighting based on long-term model-observation
449 agreement. Observation errors that include both bias and variance are more
450 difficult to incorporate and requires a model or estimate of observation bias
451 (that can be removed from the data or used to specify confidence metrics).

452 Further, analysis of model performance at both buoy locations demon-
453 strated much higher errors at the near-shore location due to more complicated
454 physics and nonlinear interactions. Improving the resolution of near-shore
455 dynamics in third-generation wave models is an active area of research. It
456 is plausible in a coastal wave model that one may be more interested in ac-
457 curately forecasting near-shore processes than those in the open bay. With
458 a sufficiently dense network of near-shore sensors, aggregation can be tuned
459 to specific forecasting requirements. The framework can be readily extended
460 with a weighting or confidence metric on individual sensor or stations based
461 on such considerations.

462 These results demonstrated the viability of combining data-driven ensem-
463 ble aggregation techniques with lightweight surrogate-model approaches to

464 improve predictive skill. The nominal computational expense of the machine-
465 learning forecasting model means there is no real practical limit to the num-
466 ber of ensemble elements that can be generated (generating a seven-day fore-
467 cast takes a fraction of a second). Recall that training the machine learning
468 model on simulated data from a physics-based wave model (SWAN) estab-
469 lished an upper limit on accuracy equal to that of the SWAN model, i. e., the
470 surrogate model was trained to reproduce SWAN-predicted ocean waves and
471 not real-world data as is generally the case in machine learning. However, by
472 combining the surrogate model with ensemble-aggregation approaches that
473 compute individual model weights based on predictive skill, this shortcoming
474 can be overcome.

475 **4. Conclusions**

476 In this paper, we detailed the creation and generation of ensemble pre-
477 dictions using a lightweight, machine-learning model. Identified limitations
478 of the surrogate model were addressed by developing ensemble-aggregation
479 techniques to minimise MSE against available measured data. RR and EG
480 aggregating algorithms computed deterministic forecasts from the ensem-
481 ble that leveraged past observations and past performance of each ensemble
482 model. Results demonstrated that the aggregating forecaster notably re-
483 duced error against observations and it represents a valuable framework to
484 integrate sparse sensor data with lightweight, data-driven surrogate models.

485 One of the primary advantages of this approach is that it provides a non-
486 invasive method to leverage data to improve forecasts. As the algorithm only
487 acts on outputs from the model to compute weighted-sum predictions, it does

488 not require any update or propagation of the model state as is necessary with
489 traditional data-assimilation approaches (and extremely difficult to integrate
490 with machine-learning-based models) making it relatively straightforward to
491 implement. Further, the aggregation algorithms can be readily replaced with
492 alternative local-minima approaches that better reflect the needs of a partic-
493 ular study (e. g., gradient-descent approaches, etc.).

494 A promising aspect of the approach not discussed here is the potential of
495 using this framework to investigate long-term processes like the multi-decadal
496 geosciences study by Arandia et al. [40]. Computationally lightweight surro-
497 gate models provide opportunity to investigate system dynamics across long
498 time scales much easier than would be possible with large-scale models. The
499 accuracy of these surrogate models can be improved with ensemble aggrega-
500 tion methods as presented here.

501 Ensemble-based forecasting is a widely used technique that accounts for
502 uncertainty inherent in numerical modelling studies. Leveraging multiple
503 simulations that encompass a wide range of potential scenarios facilitates
504 an expanded exploration of likely future conditions and provides probabilis-
505 tic information on forecasts. Many decision processes however, require a
506 single, deterministic forecast. This is typically done with some form of aver-
507 aging across all ensemble members or selection of the best individual model
508 (based on some metric). The approach presented here outlines a compre-
509 hensive technique that leverages information from past model performance
510 and observations to aggregate ensemble elements into a single forecast. The
511 non-invasive framework can be easily integrated into an on-line operational
512 forecasting system. This can be readily extended to other models and in

513 particular to combining and aggregating models with different levels of com-
514 plexity and different fundamental physics (e. g., combining rule-based models
515 with data-driven models or deterministic approaches with stochastic). Future
516 work will consider aggregation approaches that integrate models of different
517 complexity and confidence metrics to provide prior information to the ag-
518 gregating technique and parameterisation. Approaches that also consider
519 sensor uncertainty and bias can extend the applicability of the framework
520 for operational forecasting.

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525 **References**

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